

Non-Parametric Correlation Modeling of Phonocardiogram Features and Troponin Test in Myocardial Infarction Detection Using Principal Component

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Myocardial Infarction (MI) is a condition that necessitates prompt medical intervention. Current examinations using ECG and Troponin-test have the disadvantage of diagnosing MI. ECG monitoring should be continued for 12 to 24 hours until negative biomarkers have ruled out acute MI. The Cardiac Troponin test costs 282 USD. Phonocardiograms (PCG) represent the physiological and pathological cardiac, with the data acquisition each cycle is 0.8 s. This research aim to develop a non-parametric correlation model between PCG-MI signal feature results and the troponin tests. The signals were obtained from 52 Indonesian patients using an electronic stethoscope. The aquired signals in (.wav) were extracted into each cycle, time, and statistical domains. Then, all features were processed using mutual information to eliminate redundancies between features. Twelve selected features were tested for normality of distribution using Spahiro-Wilk. The Mann-Whitney U test assessed a statistically significant difference between the two independent groups. Furthermore, the strength of the association between ordinal variables was analyzed using Spearman's rank correlation. The Principal component regression was used to model the relationship between the feature and troponin test. Then we found that 12 features were categorized into non-normal distributions. The correlation test between STEMI and NSTEMI features resulted in insignificantly correlated, which suggesting feasibility of the model. The proposed principal component modeling achieved an accuracy of 91.07% for micro, 85.46% for small, 86.80% for medium, and 80.50% for large in STEMI prediction, 81.50% for micro, 75.50% for small, 84.28% for medium, and 82.50% for large in NSTEMI prediction. Multivariate analysis aligning with earlier studies on the features of PCG signals, have been represented by transfer functions. This study can serve as a basis for clarifying patients exhibiting pathological symptoms for MI detection. Our future research will focus on identifying MI signal patterns in-depth and exploring potential machine learning.

Keywords: features, myocardial infarction, phonocardiogram, principal component, troponin-test

